

THE EXPERIENCE OF STUDYING SAMPLE FOREIGN LITERATURE IN THE SYSTEM OF SECONDARY SCHOOL EDUCATION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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***Abstract.** The introduction of foreign literature samples into the education system as a whole, and in particular into the secondary and primary school education system, has long existed in the history of our national education system. We deeply understand our national Uzbek literature only by knowing the history of foreign literature. Therefore, one of the important aspects of our research is related to the use of literary subjects taught in high school to create a holistic image in the minds of learners about world literature, of which Uzbek literature is an integral part.*

***Key words:** Literature at school system, history of national Uzbek literature, teaching methods, foreign literature,*

Literature is a basic educational subject that encourages the formation of the spiritual image of the young generation and moral-spiritual research. The science of literary history plays the main role in the emotional, intellectual and aesthetic development of a schoolchild, in the understanding of existence and national identity; it is difficult to imagine the spiritual development of a nation without learning the art of artistic speech. The uniqueness of literature as a secondary school subject is determined by its essence as one of the forms of culture, more precisely, as a phenomenon: literature absorbs the world aesthetically, describes the value and diversity of human existence through artistic images. It has the ability to influence people with great power by getting to know the spiritual and aesthetic values of the nation and humanity. The introduction of foreign literature samples into the education system as a whole, and in particular into the secondary and primary school

education system, has long existed in the history of our national education system. "Most of the scholars who lived in the East-West were engaged in the practice of translation. People-loving rulers who aimed for the development of the nation gathered scholars around them and tried to create the necessary conditions for them to engage in translation. As a result, they made a great contribution to making the scientific works created in different countries become universal property, and the art and culture characteristic of one culture find its value in another culture as well."

As our great-grandfather Abu Raikhan Beruni said about his time, "all collected examples of science were translated into Arabic, processed and described, and found a place in people's hearts." In this sense, the importance of madrasahs, which received the status of higher education institution, was very important. According to historical documents and sources, 386 large and small madrasahs were operating in Central Asia from the 1st century to the beginning of the 20th century. "Among them there were small madrasahs that operated for a short time and were later closed. This number naturally changed in different periods according to changes and conditions in social and political life. The issue of studying the continuous education system established in madrasahs has attracted the attention of many scientists. However, it was not possible to reflect on the real history in this regard. Only as a result of the independence of our country, the process of true study and illumination of the history of the education system, the history of oriental science, culture, and values began and opportunities were created. Information about the history of madrasahs began to be mentioned in the recently restored pages of history. The reasons why the range of knowledge of our great ancestors, who were educated in them, could be at the encyclopedic level were clarified. Academician Boturkhan Valikhojhaev's scientific research is particularly noteworthy here. The scientist argued about the madrasahs, which played an important role in the development of Eastern science, and the educational process in them, and proved that the madrasahs are the successors of today's educational institutions with evidence from sources. In particular, on June 9-11, 2009, in Samarkand, the lectures given at the International Scientific Conference dedicated to the contribution of

Mirzo Ulugbek to the development of world science were scientifically analyzed, based on new researches and written sources, the scientist's contribution to science, political and cultural environment, and the education system. As a result, scientific research conducted on the basis of some historical documents and written sources became the basis for drawing the following conclusions: 1. The teaching methods were selected in accordance with the various fields of science taught in madrasahs, and some of the taught sciences were inextricably linked with the science of methodology. It is intended to convey, i.e. to invent and apply teaching methods. For example, the method of reading with recitation, working on vocabulary and the method of composition are among them. 2. The discovered methods were used in practice in the sciences (exact sciences) that are perceived by reason. 3. Specific methods have been devised for taking measures to master complex texts. 4. Some of these teaching methods have naturally been used to study parts related to the science of literature. During the 20th century, the list of authors recommended for teaching in high school, including the Uzbek high school education system, changes not only under the influence of purely objective-literary-artistic factors, that is, due to the appearance of new names and new works, but also under the influence of factors far from art. The reasons for inclusion or exclusion of this or that author from the school program could be different. For example, in the curriculum of all-Soviet schools adopted in 1941, there are several names of German writers: Goethe, Schiller, Heine, Feuchtwanger and others. Most of them were representatives of classical literature rejected in Germany itself or humanists who rejected the ideas of the existing German National Socialists. In the structure of this program, the main focus was actually on the contributions of world writers to literature and the high, universally recognized artistic and aesthetic level of their works. It was in the program adopted in 1941 that the appeal to artistic masterpieces was devoid of submission to overt political principles, which became primary in the programs to be adopted later.

Since the 60s of the last century, it has been observed that a purely pedagogical aspect has been developing in the teaching of foreign literature in schools of the former Union, including Uzbek. In the 1970s and 1980s, fiction, including examples

of foreign literature aimed at the aesthetic education of young people, and views on the place and role of a person in personal and social life were refined. By this time, a three-hour course introducing contemporary foreign literature is offered in 10th grade. Now, the practice of teaching the history of national Uzbek literature as an integral and integral part of the history of world literature is being implemented in the secondary school education system. The experience of reflecting the general principles of the integrated study of national literature and foreign literature at the qualitative stage, and the various processes taking place in today's world literature within the framework of secondary school curricula, has the following meaning: comparative and parallel study of national and foreign literature samples; in this case, literary similarities and parallels occur naturally through similes. Such approaches allow students to study foreign and national literature in a comparative manner, and it is very important that the historical reality reflected in the selected literary text, the raised artistic-aesthetic, literary-philosophical problems are mutually shared.

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